

Synthesis of 3, 4-dihydro-5H-pyrido [4, 3-b] indoles and 3, 4-dihydropyrimido [3, 4-a] indoles

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The Bischler-Napieralski cyclisation of N-benzoyl derivatives of 7-halo-substituted 2-(2-aminoethyl) indoles employing polyphosphate ester resulted in the formation of 1-phenyl 3,4-dihydro-5H-pyrido [4,3-b] indoles. When the 7 position of N-benzoyl derivatives of 2-(2-aminoethyl)indoles was unsubstituted, cyclisation took place in 1 position to give 1-phenyl 3,4-dihydropyrimido[3,4-a]-indoles exclusively.

RECENTLY Cohen and co-workers¹ reported the synthesis of several halogen substituted 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-*r*-carbolines. The strong antiserotonin activity of these compounds were correlated to their structural similarity with 5-benzyloxygramine and 5-chloro-2-methylgramine. In continuation of our effort² to obtain more potent antiserotonin drugs, we wish to report here the synthesis of some halogen substituted 1-phenyl 3,4-dihydro-*r*-carboline derivatives. Substituted 2-(2-aminoethyl) indoles required as the starting materials for this purpose were conveniently prepared from the corresponding 2-(2-nitrovinyl) indoles³ by lithium aluminium hydride reduction. 7-Chloro-2-(2-aminoethyl)-indole (Ia) was converted into the benzoyl derivative (IIa) and subjected to a Bischler-Napieralski cyclisation using polyphosphate ester⁴ (PPE) to get the expected 1-phenyl 3,4-dihydro-6-chloro-5H-pyrido[4,3-b]indole (IIIa). This compound showed u.v. absorption maxima at 227, 279, 317 and 384 m μ . It also exhibited a medium strong band at 3180 cm⁻¹ in the i.r. spectrum due to the free NH stretching vibration of the indole part of the molecule. The 3,4-dihydropyridoindoles (IIIa-c) thus prepared are described in table 2, and are found to exhibit similar u.v. absorption pattern and characteristic i.r. absorption band due to NH stretching vibration. The N-benzoyl derivative of 5-bromo-2-(2-aminoethyl) indole (IIf) when cyclised with polyphosphate ester (PPE) under similar conditions gave a yellow solid with high melting point (m.p. 231°-232°), whose u.v. spectrum showed absorption maxima at 223, 280, 325 and 373 m μ . The u.v. absorption curve was similar to the absorption curves of the 3,4-dihydro-*r*-carbolines described earlier (IIIa-c). The i.r. spectrum of this compound surprisingly did not show the NH absorption frequency. Nevertheless, the elemental analysis of this compound was in full agreement with the presumed dihydro-*r*-carboline structure and absence

For I and II	For III	For IV
R =	R =	R =
a; 7-Cl	a; 6-Cl	d; 7-Br
b; 7-Br	b; 6-Br	e; 7-Cl
c; 5-Me, 7-Br	c; 8-Me, 6-Br	f; 6-Cl
d; 4-Cl		
e; 5-Cl		
f; 5-Br		

of NH absorption in the i.r. indicated that the cyclisation must have taken place at position 1 of the indole nucleus. This was supported by the NMR spectrum (100 MHz) in deuterated dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) taking tetramethylsilane (TMS) as the reference standard. The spectrum exhibited two 1:2:1 triplets at τ 7.08 and 6.15 respectively due to the two adjacent methylene protons present in the dihydropyrimidine ring, and the nine protons in the aromatic region from τ 2.29 to 3.15. Out of the nine aromatic protons, five are from the phenyl group

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attached to the dihydropyrimidine ring and three from the benzene ring of the indole nucleus. Obviously, the ninth proton in the β -proton of the pyrrole part of the indole molecule, the location of which could not be traced due to its being shifted to down-fields and being buried in the complex aromatic signals because of the polar solvent effect of DMSO. Moreover, if the ninth proton were NH, it would in DMSO, have appeared far below $-\tau 1.00^5$, the fact which indeed is supported by the absence of NH absorption band in i.r.

The coupling constants of the methylene protons threw more light on the position of this ninth proton. In addition to its coupling with the adjacent methylene group with a coupling constant of 8.00 Hz, the higher field methylene protons (at $\tau 7.08$) were further split by a small coupling of 2.00 Hz indicating *meta* coupling with the—CH proton. This observation could be correctly accounted for only by the free β -proton which is in *meta* relationship with the higher field methylene group of the dihydropyrimidine ring system (IVd).

In order to accomplish the basis for the above arguments and to enunciate a complete discussion

of the subject, the NMR of compound IVd was compared with that of one of the dihydro-*r*-carbolines discussed earlier. 6-Chloro-1-phenyl-3,4-dihydro-*r*-carboline (IIIa), exhibited, as required, only the eight protons in the aromatic region ranging from $\tau 2.30$ to 3.38 (unlike nine protons as in the case of NMR spectrum of IVd). The five protons present on the pyridine ring of the *r*-carboline molecule together appeared as a singlet ($\tau 2.43$) accounting for a spaciouly occupied phenyl ring without any steric hindrance, confirming the cyclisation to have taken place at position 3 of the indole nucleus. Similarly, the NMR spectrum of 6-bromo-1-phenyl-3,4-dihydro-*r*-carboline (IIIb), also exhibited the presence of eight protons in the aromatic region, five of which appeared as a sharp singlet at $\tau 2.43$ and the remaining three protons ranged from $\tau 2.70$ to 3.45, confirming once again, that cyclisation had taken place at the β -position of the indole ring. Very recently, Cohen and co-workers⁶ have reported the synthesis of several pyrimido[3,4-*a*]indoles directly by the Fischer cyclisation of 1,3-disubstituted 4-piperidone phenylhydrazones⁷ or by the cyclisation of 2-isotryptamine derivatives on heating with benzaldehyde. Our observations are in agreement with discussions of the NMR spectra of dihydropyrimidoindoles reported by these authors⁶.

From the above discussions it is evident that when the benzoyl derivative of 7 halogen (Cl or Br) substituted 2-(2-aminoethyl) indole (IIa-c) was subjected to Bischler-Napieralski cyclodehydration with polyphosphate ester (PPE), cyclisation took place at position 3 of the indole molecule giving rise to 3,4-dihydro-5H-pyrido[4,3-*b*]indole ring system (IIIa-c) exclusively. The other possibility, viz., the cyclisation taking place at 1 position of the indole molecule did not occur probably due to the steric hindrance by the halogen (Cl or Br) substituent present on 7 position of the N-benzoyl derivatives of 2-isotryptamines (IIa-c). On the other hand, if the 7 position of the N-benzoyl derivatives of 2-isotryptamines (II d-f) was unsubstituted, obviously cyclisation took place at 1 position of indole molecule yielding 3,4-dihydropyrimido [3,4-*a*]indoles (IVd-f).

Experimental

The u.v. spectra were recorded in ethanol on a Hilger Uvispek H-700 spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched quartz cells. IR spectra were recorded in Nujol mull on a Carl Zeiss UR-10 spectrometer. NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO- D_6 using TMS as the internal reference standard.

Preparation of starting materials: Various *Bz*-substituted 2-(2-aminoethyl) indoles were prepared by lithium aluminium hydride reduction of the corresponding 2-(2-nitrovinyl) indoles according to the procedure described earlier³.

Preparation of the benzoyl derivative of 2-(2-aminoethyl) indoles: A mixture of 7-chloro-2-(2-aminoethyl) indole (3.5 g.), benzoyl chloride (2.8 g.) and aqueous sodium hydroxide (15%, 30 ml.) was stirred vigorously with occasional cooling till a viscous solid separated. It was collected, washed with small quantity of ether and finally with water and dried. The crude product was passed through alumina column, eluting with benzene. The product was further crystallised from benzene or benzene petroleum ether (40°–60°). The benzoyl derivatives thus prepared are described in Table 1.

Preparation of polyphosphate ester (PPE^{4a}): A mixture of dry chloroform (25 ml.) and absolute ether (50 ml.) was added to pure phosphorus pentoxide (20 g.). The mixture was gently refluxed for 30–40 hr., till all phosphorus pentoxide dissolved to form clear syrupy liquid. It was decanted and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure at room temperature. The colourless syrupy polyphosphate ester thus obtained was used immediately for cyclisation purpose.

*3,4-Dihydro-5H-pyrido[4,3-*b*]indoles:* A solution of benzoyl derivative of 7-chloro-2-(2-aminoethyl) indole (4 g.) in dry chloroform (200 ml.) was added to PPE (20 g.) and the mixture refluxed for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was kept overnight at room temperature. The solvent was removed by distillation under reduced pressure and the remaining dark brown oil was poured into ice cold water (200 ml.) with vigorous stirring and the mixture stirred for 2 hr. more. The

TABLE 1—BENZOYL DERIVATIVES OF 2-(2-AMINOETHYL) INDOLES (IIa-f)

Compd.	M.P.	Found(%)			Molecular formula	Calcd.(%)		
		C	H	N		C	H	N
IIa	197°	68.21	5.32	9.20	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ OCl	68.36	5.03	9.38
IIb	150°-151°(decomp.)	59.35	4.00	7.80	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ OBr	59.50	4.37	8.17
IIc	85°-87° (decomp.)	60.21	4.40	7.52	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₂ OBr	60.53	4.76	7.85
IIId	162°	68.18	5.11	9.67	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ OCl	68.36	5.03	9.38
IIe	192°	68.10	5.51	9.61	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ OCl	68.36	5.03	9.38
IIIf	171°	59.23	4.51	8.31	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ OBr	59.50	4.37	8.17

TABLE 2 —1-PHENYL 3,4-DIHYDRO-5H-PYRIDO[4.3-b]INDOLES (IIIa-c)

Compd.	M.P.	Found(%)			Molecular formula	Calc.(%)			U.V. spectra (Ethanol) m μ log ϵ	I.R. spectra (cm ⁻¹)	N.M.R. spectra (τ)* (DMSO-D ₆)	
		C	H	N		C	H	N				
IIIa	288-289°	72.91	4.20	9.99	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ Cl	72.74	4.63	9.98	227	4.43	6 20 (2H, <i>t</i> , J _{C2, CH2} = 8.0 Hz, CH ₂ of pyridine ring)	
									279	3.985		
									317	3.58		7.05 (2H, <i>t</i> , J _{CH2, CH2} = 8.0 Hz, CH ₂ of pyridine ring)
									384	3.68		2 30 to 3.38 (8H, <i>m</i> , aromatic signals)
IIIb	274-275°	63.10	3.80	8.40	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ Br	62.79	4.00	8.62	226	4.48	6 21 (2H, <i>t</i> , J _{CH2, CH2} = 8.0 Hz, CH ₂ of pyridine ring)	
									280	4.13		
									321	3.795		7.06 (2H, <i>t</i> , J _{CH2, CH2} = 8.0 Hz, CH ₂ of pyridine ring)
									378	3.865		2 32 to 3.45 (8H, <i>m</i> , aromatic signals)
IIIc	270-271°	63.48	4.31	8.38	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₂ Br	63.74	4.43	8.26	226	4.45	2 43 (5H, <i>s</i> , Ph. gr. attached to pyridine ring).	
									283	4.05		
									324	3.65		
									379	3.77		

* *s* = singlet; *t* = triplet; *m* = multiplet.

TABLE 3—1-PHENYL 3,4-DIHYDROPYRIMIDO[3,4-a]INDOLES* (IVd-f)

Compd.	M.P.	Found(%)			Molecular formula	Calc(%)			U.V. spectra (Ethanol)		N.M.R. spectra (τ)** (DMSO-D ₆)	
		C	H	N		C	H	N	m μ	log ϵ		
IVd	231-232°	62.95	4.20	8.71	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ Br	62.79	4.00	8.62	223	4.426	6.15 (2H, t, J _{CH₂, CH₂=}	
									280	4.03		8.0 Hz, lower CH ₂
									325	3.69		
									373	3.72		
										7.08 (2H, t, J _{CH₂, CH₂=}		
										8.0 Hz, higher CH ₂		
										of pyrimidine ring).		
										2.29 to 3.15 (9H, m,		
										aromatic signals).		
IVe	245°	72.41	4.70	9.76	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ Cl	72.74	4.63	9.98	225	4.425	—	
									280	3.95		
									329	3.55		
									370	3.70		
IVf	222°	72.52	4.30	9.71	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ Cl	72.74	4.63	9.98	224	4.325	—	
									227	4.025		
									324	3.515		
									381	3.84		

* I.R. spectra of IV(d-f) in Nujol mull did not show any band due to N-H absorption.

** t = triplet; m = multiplet.

clear solution was decanted and rendered alkaline by adding aqueous sodium hydroxide (15%). The pale yellow solid which separated was collected, washed with water and dried. The product was crystallised from appropriate solvent. The 3,4-dihydro-5H-pyrido[4,3-b]indoles thus prepared are described in Table 2.

3,4-Dihydropyrimido[3,4-a]indoles: A solution of benzoyl derivative of 5-bromo-2-(2-aminoethyl)indole (4.1 g.) in dry chloroform (200 ml.) was added to polyphosphate ester (20 g.). The mixture was gently refluxed for 1 hr. and then allowed to stand over night. The solvent was removed under diminished pressure and the residue gradually poured into ice cold water (200 ml.) with vigorous stirring. After 2 hr. stirring, the clear solution was decanted and made alkaline with sodium hydroxide (15%). The yellow solid which separated was collected, dried and the product crystallised from suitable solvent. The pyrimidoindoles thus prepared are described in Table 3.

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